

CONDITIONS FOR IMPROVING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FIELD OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: A distinctive feature of modernized education is the improvement of innovative technologies, bringing the process of independent learning to a new qualitative level. For this, it is important to study the richest pedagogical experiences in this area, to organize the conditions for applying these experiences.

Keywords. This article studies the conditions and conditions for improving the methodology for developing students' independent learning competencies in the credit-module system.

Many studies have addressed the conditions for developing students' independent learning activities. In research, motivation is emphasized as the most important condition for activating students' learning activities.

The article considers the conditions for activating students' independent learning activities. In this case, motivation is manifested as the basis of independent learning activities. Motivations are the basis of students' independent learning activities, since motivational and need-based activities, together with the socio-economic environment of a person, determine the activity of a person to improve his knowledge and skills. The important role of motivation in education has been emphasized by many authors. For example, Ya.L.Kolominsky gives an example of how motivation affects the attitude of a person to the task he has set for himself.

The system of motives includes needs (the subject's motivation for activity related to satisfying their needs), interests (any impulse towards activity, a reason perceived on the basis of which a person chooses practical actions and aspirations), goals (a set of external or internal conditions that activate the subject and determine its direction) and their complex interrelation (mental phenomena that become an incentive for the implementation of behavior) and influence (a trajectory of action that encourages and determines the choice of a direction of activity). Motives can be noted as the basis of independent knowledge acquisition activities. The concept of motive is studied by scientific psychologists from different perspectives.

Thus, motives are of great importance in the development of activities that serve independent knowledge acquisition. Motivation for independent knowledge acquisition is considered a specific type of educational motivation. Motivation serves to consciously control activity, which is manifested in overcoming difficulties and obstacles to achieve a specific goal.